

An Application of the Gattermann-Adams Reaction to *o*-Hydroxyphenyl Benzyl Ketones

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Farkas method of isoflavone synthesis works fairly satisfactorily with deoxybenzoins derived from reserpinol or hydroxyquinol. If aluminium chloride is added, as was done by Kawase, nuclear formylation takes place even in these cases. Phloroglucinol derivatives undergo only nuclear formylation under all conditions.

The most widely used method for isoflavone synthesis starts with an appropriate deoxybenzoin and introduces a single carbon atom as an aldehyde or *o*-hydroxymethylene in the reactive methylene group followed by ring closure. For this purpose, ethyl formate was first used successfully and it is quite suitable when free hydroxy groups are not many¹. Methyl formate² and ethyl orthoformate³ are similar in behaviour. In cases where free hydroxy groups are present in a deoxybenzoin, ethoxalyl chloride has been most successful.⁴ In the ethoxalyl chloride method, esterification of free hydroxy groups may take place first, followed by the Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement in presence of a base and final ring closure. This mechanism is supported by the recent experiments of Gupta and Seshadri⁵ on the reaction of a deoxybenzoin with acetyl chloride and pyridine when a phenyl acetate resulted. Subsequent facile acetyl migration and ring closure occurred in presence of either aqueous or anhydrous potassium carbonate. Actually for the synthesis of 2-alkyl or 2-aryl isoflavones, the most convenient method is to treat the *o*-hydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone with the acid chloride, dry acetone, and potassium carbonate. The use of formamide or formanilide has been examined and is found to be of limited applicability.⁶ A very recent observation has been made by Chakravarti *et al.*⁷ that 2,4-dihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone when allowed to react with methylene iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide solution affords 7-hydroxy isoflavanone which undergoes smooth oxidation with selenium dioxide to yield 7-hydroxyisoflavone. Its general applicability has, however, yet to be examined. With all these reagents, the reactivity of the methylene group is utilized and basic condensing agents are employed. They work well under conditions when the activity of the nuclear positions of the benzene ring is not so high as to interfere or create complications.

Recently Farkas⁸ has suggested a method wherein he used what may be described as the Gattermann-Adams reagent, viz., zinc cyanide and dry hydrogen chloride. Thus,

1. Spath and Lederer, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 747; Joshi and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 513.
2. Narasimhachari, *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 347; 1953, 12B, 287.
3. Sathe and Venkataraman, *Curr. Sci.*, 1949, 19, 373.
4. Baker *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1852.
5. Gupta and Seshadri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 10B, 116.
6. Gowan *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2495.
7. Chakravarti *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1961, 27, 407.
8. Farkas, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 1212; *Ber.*, 1957, 90, 2040.

using the appropriate deoxybenzoin, Farkas⁹ synthesized successfully 7-hydroxy-, 7-methoxy-, 7,4'-dihydroxy-isoflavones and Farkas *et al.*⁹ prepared 7-hydroxy-3', 4'-dimethoxyisoflavone, ψ -baptigenin, and formononetin. This method has also been used for the synthesis of afromosin¹⁰(7-hydroxy-6,4'-dimethoxy-isoflavone) which occurs in *Afromosia elata*.

Here is a reaction which has been used generally for introducing a formyl group in the aromatic nucleus and it has been employed recently by Farkas successfully for the reaction with an active methylene group of a deoxybenzoin. A study has therefore been made of the scope of this reaction and most appropriate conditions for its success. As our work was in progress, Kawase *et al.*¹¹ reported that they had failed in the use of this method for the preparation of isoflavones. Our experiments using 2,4-dihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone and 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone confirm the findings of Farkas *et al.*⁹ and the method can therefore be used for the deoxybenzoin based on the resorcinol system which they have mentioned. The failure of Kawase *et al.*¹¹ is due to the difference in the conditions they employed; Farkas employed only zinc cyanide and in this case the methylene reactivity is adequate as compared with that of the resorcylic nucleus for undergoing condensation to yield isoflavones. The poor yield of the isoflavone indicates, however, that side reactions are taking place. On the other hand, Kawase *et al.*¹¹ employed a mixture of zinc cyanide and anhydrous aluminium chloride, a combination most suited for nuclear activity of the γ -position. Earlier, considerable work has been done with carbonyl derivatives of resorcinol using this combination and the products were γ -formyl derivatives.¹² In the present experiments also, 2,4-dihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone when subjected to these conditions gives the 3-formyl derivative as reported by Kawase *et al.*¹¹. An additional case of 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone (I) has also been studied under similar conditions. Again, the 3-formyl derivative (II) is formed. Its constitution has been supported by catalytic reduction with hydrogen in presence of palladium-charcoal when the product is found identical with the 3-methyl compound (III) prepared according to the procedure of Krishnamurti and Seshadri¹³. Further confirmation has been obtained by partial methylation of (III) when 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone (IV) is obtained. This has been prepared by another method involving nuclear methylation of 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone (I) under the same conditions as used for a similar methylation of carbonyl derivatives of resorcinol.¹⁴ The *C*-methyl compound (IV) has also been converted into 8-methyl-7,4'-dimethoxyisoflavone (V), identical with an authentic sample prepared by Krishnamurti *et al.*¹³.

The successful synthesis of afromosin by McMurry and Theng¹⁰ under the conditions of Farkas would suggest that in the 2,4,5-trihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketones also, the reactivity is essentially that of resorcinol and the formation of isoflavone takes place. Possibly an explanation for the comparatively low yield of the Farkas procedure may be found in the competitive reactivity of the benzene ring. This feature becomes much more

9. Farkas *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1956, **91**, 2858.

10. McMurry and Theng, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1491.

11. Kawase, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1958, **31**, 907; *Chem. Abst.*, 1959, **53**, 18018d.

12. Shah and Shah, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1939, 132.

13. Krishnamurti and Seshadri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 259.

14. Rangaswami and Seshadri, *Proc., Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, **8A**, 214.

pronounced when a phloroglucinol system is employed. Thus when, 2,4,6-trihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone (VIa) is used, even the Farkas procedure, not involving the use of aluminium chloride, does not yield any isoflavone, but produces only 3-formyldeoxybenzoin

(VIIa). This product has been characterized by reduction to the *O*-methyl compound which is identical with an authentic sample of 3-*O*-methyl-2, 4, 6-trihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone (VIIa)¹⁵. It may be mentioned that even the dimethyl ether (VIb) of the above deoxybenzoin (VIa) behaves similarly indicating that the presence of methoxyls is sufficient to bring about the necessary activation of the benzene ring.

*EXPERIMENTAL

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-formylphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl Ketone (II).—A mixture of 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzylketone¹⁶ (2.0 g.), zinc cyanide (2.5 g.), and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) in dry ether (100 ml) was stirred and saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 0-5° during a period of 4 hrs. After keeping it overnight, the oil was washed with dry ether, dissolved in aqueous ethanol (50%, 50 ml), heated at 70-75° for 2 hours, and then cooled. The solid product (0.7 g.) was filtered and crystallised from methanol when 2,4-dihydroxy-3-formylphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone separated as colorless, stout elongated rectangular prisms, m.p. 114-15°, λ_{max} 248, 274 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.33, 4.28), λ_{inflec} 320 m μ , ($\log \epsilon$ 3.69). (Found : C, 66.9; H, 5.4. C₁₆H₁₄O₅ requires C, 67.1; H, 4.9%). It gave a red colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methylphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl Ketone (III).—A solution of the above formyl derivative (II) (0.2 g.) in acetic acid (50 ml) was treated with Pd-C (5%, 0.3 g.) and the mixture kept stirred in an atmosphere of hydrogen at room temperature and under atmospheric pressure, when it absorbed hydrogen (120 ml). It was filtered, washed with acetic acid, and the filtrate evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. Water (50 ml) was added to the residue and the solid (0.15 g.) filtered. It crystallised from ethanol as shining rods and needles, m.p. 172-73° alone or when mixed with a synthetic sample prepared by the method of Krishnamurti and Seshadri.¹³ It gave a purple colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl Ketone (IV).—(i) A solution of 2,4-dihydroxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone (3 g.) in absolute methanolic potash (4 g. in 23 ml) was cooled in a bath of ice-salt mixture and treated with ice-cold methyl iodide (7.5 ml) in one lot. The mixture was well shaken to render it homogeneous and then left in the ice bath to attain room temperature gradually. Next day the mixture was gently refluxed for 7 hrs. and then diluted with water (100 ml). The resulting solution was extracted with ether and the ether solution was washed with 5% aqueous sodium carbonate followed by water. The ethereal solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue treated with methanol (25 ml). The solid (1.3 g) separating on standing was filtered and recrystallised from methanol when it formed rhombohedral prisms and tablets, m.p. 116-17° (Krishnamurti and Seshadri¹³ report m.p. 121-22°). (ii). Partial methylation of 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methyl phenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone (III) as effected by Krishnamurti and Seshadri¹³ yielded rhombohedral prisms and tablets, m. p. 116-17° alone or when mixed with the above sample.

*Ultraviolet spectra were taken in 95% ethanolic solution. Melting points are uncorrected.

15. Ienger *et al.*, Mehta, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B 166.

16. Baker and Eastwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2902

7,4'-Dimethoxy-8-methylisoflavone (V).—The above deoxybenzoin (IV) (0.5 g.) was condensed with ethyl formate (50 ml) in presence of sodium (0.5 g.) as described by Krishnamurti and Seshadri¹³. The crude product was dissolved in benzene and purified by chromatography using a column of alumina and benzene as the eluting solvent. The benzene solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum affording the isoflavone (V) in the form of rhombic and rhombohedral plates, m.p. 144-45° alone or when mixed with the sample of Krishnamurti and Seshadri¹³.

2,4,6-Trihydroxy-3-formylphenylbenzyl Ketone (VIIa).—A suspension of 2,4,6-trihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone¹⁷ (3g.) and zinc cyanide (3g.) in dry ether (50 ml) was saturated with dry HCl gas as mentioned in a similar case earlier. The aldimine hydrochloride was hydrolysed with ethanol (50%, 100 ml) at 70-75° for 2 hrs. and the product extracted with benzene. The benzene residue (0.6g.) crystallised from benzene-light petroleum mixture as colorless small prisms, m.p. 95-96°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 275 m μ , ($\log \epsilon$ 4.53). (Found: C, 65.8; H, 4.4. C₁₅H₁₂O₅ requires C, 66.2; H, 4.4%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol as red crystals, m.p. 180-82°. The aldehyde gave a deep red colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

When the above experiment was repeated using zinc cyanide (4 g.) and aluminium chloride (3 g.) mixture and the product worked up as in the above case, the product (0.6g) was obtained as colorless small prisms, m.p. 95-96° alone or when mixed with the above sample.

2,4,6-Trihydroxy-3-methylphenylbenzyl Ketone (VIIIa).—The above formyl derivative (VIIa) (0.5 g.) was reduced with hydrogen (180 ml) in acetic acid (25 ml) using Pd-C (5%, 0.5g.) and the product worked up as described earlier. The 3-methyldeoxybenzoin (VIIIa) crystallised from dilute ethanol as colorless flat needles and rectangular plates, m.p. 198-96° alone or when mixed with the sample of Iengar *et al.*¹⁵.

2-Hydroxy-3-formyl-4,6-dimethoxyphenylbenzyl Ketone (VIIb).—A steady stream of dry HCl was passed through a mixture of 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyphenylbenzyl ketone¹⁸ (3 g.) and zinc cyanide (3 g.) in dry ether (250 ml) as mentioned above. The product after working up crystallised from ethanol as colorless broad rectangular plates (1.8 g.), m.p. 146-47°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 269, 293 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.20, 4.24). (Found: C, 67.6; H, 5.5. C₁₇H₁₆O₅ requires C, 68.0. H, 5.3%). It gave a red colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-4,6-dimethoxyphenylbenzyl Ketone (VIIIb).—The above formyl derivative (0.7 g.) was reduced with hydrogen (250 ml) in acetic acid (50 ml) solution using Pd-C (5%, 0.8 g.) as the catalyst and the product worked up as described earlier. The 3-methyldeoxybenzoin (0.6 g.) crystallised from methanol as colorless square plates, m.p., 153-54° alone or when mixed with the sample prepared by the method of Iengar *et al.*¹⁵.

17. Chapman and Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 408.

18. Badcock *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2964.